

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL LIPSTICK

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ABSTRACT

Herbal lipsticks are color and protection giving to lips using natural ingredients like herbal extracts, natural colorants and essential oils. The herbal lipstick is devoid of side effects and nourishes the lips with the additives. In the present study, we aimed to prepare a lipstick with natural colorants and essential oils and evaluated by color, pH, melting point, breaking point, spreadability test, aging stability and smudge test. The present study concluded that the use of natural ingredients in herbal lipstick have no side effects and more consumer acceptance.

KEYWORDS: Herbal lipstick, colorants, essential oils.

INTRODUCTION

Herbal lipstick is a natural cosmetic product prepared using plant based ingredients such as herbal colorants, natural oils, waxes and butter. It enhances lip beauty while providing nourishment and protection. Unlike normal lipsticks that contain synthetic dyes and chemicals, herbal lipsticks are safer, non-irritating, eco-friendly and suitable for sensitive skin. They offer moisturizing, healing and antioxidant benefits, making them a healthier alternative to conventional lipsticks.

OBJECTIVES

- To provide safe and natural lip coloration.
- To nourish and protect lips from dryness and cracking.
- To avoid side effects caused by synthetic dyes and preservatives.
- Evaluation of the prepared lipstick by color, pH, melting point, breaking point, spreadability test, aging stability and smudge test.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MASTER FORMULA –PATHIMUKHAM MATTE RED LIPSTICK(100g)

ingredients	Weight in grams
Bees wax	28
Carnauba wax	2
Coca butter	20
Almond oil	20
Castor oil	12
Coconut oil	8
Concentrated Pathimukham extract	4
Concentrated amaranth extract	4
Arrow root powder	2
Vitamin E	0.2 (5-8 drops)
Rose oil	0.1 (2-3 drops)

Preparation of Pathimukham extract

The botanical name for pathimukham is *Caesalpinia sappan*. It is also known as sappanwood, Indian red wood or patang

Botanical name: *Caesalpinia sappan*

Common name : Sappan wood, Indian red wood, patang

Family : Fabaceae

Take 20 g of Pathimukham wood chips. Add 100ml of water. Boil under it volume reduces to 30ml. Filter through muslin cloth. Continue heating until it becomes thick concentrated extract. Cool completely. This extract gives the deep red tone instead of pink.

beaker of water. Heat gradually and note the temperature at which the lipstick starts to melt.

Preparation of Amaranth extract

Genus – *Amaranthus*

Species- *A.tricolor*

A.dubius

A.lividus

Take 20g of aerial parts of amaranth plant. Add 100 ml of water Boil under it volume reduces to 30ml. Filter through muslin cloth. Continue heating until it becomes thick concentrated extract. Cool completely.

Breaking point

Fix the lipstick in a holder leaving 1 inch sample out. Apply weight gradually at the top. Note the weight at which the lipstick breaks.

Spreadability test

Take a clean glass slide and mark a 1cm² area. Apply a uniform thin layer of lipstick over the marked area. Place another glass slide on the top. Keep a standard weight over the top slide for 1 minute. Remove the weight and upper slide carefully. Measure the diameter or area of lipstick spread

$$\text{Spreadability} = \frac{\text{Increased area of spread (cm}^2\text{)}}{\text{Initial area (cm}^2\text{)}}$$

pH determination

Dissolve 1g lipstick in 10ml ethanol. Add 10ml distilled water. Shake and filter. Measure the pH using pH meter.

Smudge test

Apply lipstick on a glass slide. Press with filter paper. Note the amount of color transferred.

Aging stability test

Store lipstick at different conditions

5°C (Fridge), 25°C (room temperature) & 40°C (accelerated stability).

Observe for 3-7 days. Check for changes in color, hardness, sweating and odor.

Preparation of Lipstick

Set up a boiler. Add bees wax and carnauba wax. Heat gently until dissolved. Do not overheat (avoid temperature >80°C)

Add almond oil, castor oil and coconut oil. Mix well for uniform consistency. Add concentrated Pathimukham extract. Mix until the mixture is uniform red. Add 2g of arrow root powder. Maintain temperature ~60°C while mixing. Cool mixture to 45-50°C. Add Vitamin E drops and rose oil. Mix gently. Pour the molten lipstick mass into lipstick mold. Allow to cool at room temperature 15 minutes. Place in a refrigerator for 10 minutes to harden.

Evaluation of Lipstick**Melting point**

Take a small piece of lipstick and place it in a capillary tube. Attach the tube to a thermometer. Immerse in a

RESULTS

Evaluation parameters	Results	Normal values
Melting point	63°C	55°C-75°C
Breaking point	300g	250-400g
Spreadability test	1.2	1.1-1.8
pH determination	6.3	4.5-7.0
Smudge test	Moderate smudge	Acceptable
Aging stability test	No sweating No cracking No color/odor change No separation of oils Consistent hardness and smoothness	Stable

CONCLUSION

The herbal lipstick was successfully formulated using natural ingredients such as herbal pigments, oils and waxes. The prepared formulation exhibited good physical appearance, uniform color, smooth texture and acceptable fragrance. Evaluation test including melting point, breaking point, spreadability, smudge test, aging stability and pH showed that the lipstick meets standard cosmetic quality parameters. Overall, the study concludes that the formulated herbal lipstick is stable, safe, aesthetically appealing and a promising natural alternative to synthetic commercial lipsticks, offering both cosmetic benefits and reduced chemical exposure.

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